

N,N-Disubstituted- β -Methyl-*p*-Methoxy Cinnamamides, as Possible CNS Depressants

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In view of the expected ease of decarboxylation of β -(4-methoxyphenyl)glutaconic anhydride in basic condition with secondary amines, it was realised that they could be converted into β -methyl substituted cinnamamide in one step reaction. These compounds showed mild CNS depressant action.

AMIDES of cinnamic acid have received considerable attention and are reported to possess a variety of pharmacological properties^{1,2}. It has been observed that β -methyl cinnamamides³ possess greater hypnotic activity. In molecular manipulation of compounds, increasing the size of the alkyl group in N,N-dialkylamine results, in general, in loss of the biological activity^{4,5}. Introduction of substituted piperazine moiety, however, enhances the biological activity. These observations prompted us to employ N-arylpiperazines alongwith other secondary amines in the nucleophilic cleavage of β -arylglutaconic anhydride ring and subsequent decarboxylation in basic condition, in an one pot reaction, to furnish N,N-disubstituted- β -methyl-*p*-methoxy cinnamamides in good yields.

3-(4-Methoxyphenyl)glutaconic acid anhydride⁶ (I) was refluxed in a low boiling, non-polar solvent like benzene with secondary amines to obtain N,N-disubstituted mono amide of 3-(4-methoxyphenyl)glutaconic acid (III). Nucleophilic cleavage of β -aryl glutaconic anhydride ring with secondary amines invariably results in the formation of compounds in which the nucleophilic residue is attached to the α,β -unsaturated carbonyl group. The structure of the compounds shown is supported by the following data. IR spectrum of IIIc (KBr)

showed two carbonyl peaks at 1710 ($-\overset{\text{O}}{\parallel}{\text{C}}-\text{OH}$) and

1610 cm^{-1} ($-\overset{\text{O}}{\parallel}{\text{C}}-\text{N}$) and OH of COOH was observed at 3000 cm^{-1} . PMR spectrum of IIIc (CDCl_3) showed a sharp singlet at δ 3.72, integrating for 8 protons of the morpholine methylene groups. The other peaks were at δ 3.8 (3H, s, Ar-OCH₃), 3.68 (2H, s, -CH₂-COOH), 6.48 (1H, s, =CH-) and two sets of doublets at δ 6.8 and 7.52 (4H, Ar-H). Decarboxylation of III by heating it to it's fusion temperature gave N,N-disubstituted- β -methyl-*p*-methoxy cinnamamide (IV). IV could also

be obtained from I in one step as the decarboxylation was facile in basic medium. When I was refluxed with an excess of a secondary amine for a longer time IV was obtained. III was smoothly decarboxylated. Structure of IVc was confirmed by the spectral data. IR spectrum of IVc (KBr) showed the absence of a carboxy peak at 1700 cm^{-1} . It showed the amide carbonyl peak at 1630 cm^{-1} . The other peaks were at 1600 (C=C), 1250 (Ar-OCH₃) and 834 cm^{-1} (trisubstituted C=C). PMR spectrum of IVc (CDCl_3) showed signals at δ 2.22 (3H, s, -CH₃), 3.63 (8H, s, CH₂ - of morpholine ring), 3.8 (3H, s, Ar-OCH₃), 6.15 (1H, s, =CH-CO) and two doublets at δ 6.8 and 7.35 due to aromatic protons each integrating for two protons, $J=9$ cps. When IV was reduced by Raney-Nickel catalyst (W-6 type) on a Parr hydrogenator at 50 psi H₂ pressure at room temp. for 6-8 hr, N,N-disubstituted-3-(4-methoxyphenyl) butanamides (V) were formed. IR spectrum of Vc (KBr) showed amide carbonyl group at 1640 cm^{-1} . Disappearance of a band at 1610 cm^{-1} indicated the absence of >C=C< . PMR spectrum of Vc (CDCl_3) showed signals at δ 1.3 (3H, d, -CH-CH₃), 1.93 (1H, m, CH₃-CH-CH₂), 2.54 (2H, m, CH-CH₂-CO-N), 3.5 [8H, m, (CH₂)₄ of morpholine ring], 3.73 (3H, s, Ar-OCH₃) and 6.7-7.3 (4H, m, Ar-H, 1,4-disubstitution pattern). The olefinic -CH was not observed. The course of the reaction is depicted in Scheme 1.

Experimental

All the melting points reported are uncorrected. The ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Backman Acculab-10 spectrophotometer (ν_{max} in cm^{-1}). PMR spectra on Varian-60 spectrometer with TMS as internal standard (chemical shifts in δ , ppm) and mass spectra on a varian Mat S-112 instrument at 70 eV energy.

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Scheme 1

Morpholine amide of 3-(4-methoxyphenyl) glutamic acid (IIIc): 3-(4-Methoxyphenyl)glutaconic anhydride⁵ (I) (2.18 g; 0.01 M) was refluxed with morpholine (0.087 ml; 0.01 M) in dry benzene for 3-4 hr and the solvent was removed. The acid was dissolved in saturated solution of sodium bicarbonate and regenerated with dilute hydrochloric acid. It was crystallized from absolute alcohol, m.p. 136-137°, yield 2.28 g (75%). (Found: C, 62.70; H, 6.05; N, 4.78. C₁₆H₁₉NO₅ requires C, 62.94; H, 6.27; N, 4.59%). Compounds IIIa to IIII were prepared by following the same procedure (Tables 1 and 2).

Morpholine amide of 3-methyl-p-methoxy cinnamic acid (IVc):

Method A: IIIc (3.05 g; 0.01 M) was heated to its melting point in an oil bath for 1 hr. It was then cooled, washed with sodium bicarbonate and water. The solid was crystallized from ethanol, m.p. 87-88°, yield 2.27 g (87%). (Found: C, 68.72; H, 7.90; N, 6.52. C₁₅H₁₉NO₃ requires C, 68.94; H, 7.81; N, 6.38%).

Method B: I (2.18 g; 0.01 M) and morpholine (1.74 ml; 0.02 M) were refluxed in an oil bath for 10-12 hr without any solvent. The reaction mixture was cooled to room temp. and poured in ice-cold water. The solid was washed with dil. hydrochloric acid and water repeatedly, and was crystallized from ethanol to yield yellowish white shining needles, m.p. 87-88°, yield 2.18 g (80%). Compounds IVa to IVI were prepared by following the same procedure (Tables 3 and 4).

Morpholine amide of 3-(4-methoxyphenyl) butanoic acid (IVc): IVc (2.61 g; 0.01 M) was dissolved in solvent ether (100 ml) and Raney-Nickel catalyst (0.5 g, W-6 type) was added to it. The compound was then reduced on a Parr hydrogenator at 50 psi pressure on H₂ gas at room temp. for 6-8 hr. After reduction, the solution was filtered to remove catalyst and the filtrate was concentrated to yield Vc. The solid was crystallized from absolute alcohol, m.p. 79-80°, yield 1.36 g (52%). (Found: C, 68.50; H, 8.01; N, 5.29. C₁₅H₂₁NO₃ requires C, 68.41; H, 8.03; N, 5.31). Compounds Va to VI were produced by following the same procedure as described above (Tables 5 and 6).

Pharmacology:

For pharmacological screening, albino mice of Haflkin strain of either sex weighing between 18-22 g were selected. The animals were kept in quarantine for 4-5 days prior to the day of the experiment. Food was withdrawn 18-24 hr prior to the actual experiment but water was given *ad libidum*.

TABLE 1—CHARACTERIZATION DATA OF N,N-DISUBSTITUTED MONO AMIDE OF 3-(4-METHOXYPHENYL)GLUTA CONIC ACID (III)

Compd.		Molecular formula	Yield %	m.p. °C	Analysis %; Found/(Calcd.)		
					C	H	N
IIIa	Dimethylamino	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ NO ₄	78	183-84	65.60 (65.19)	6.80 (6.27)	5.20 (5.12)
IIIb	Diethylamino	C ₁₆ H ₂₁ NO ₄	60	187-88	65.54 (65.96)	7.12 (7.27)	4.71 (4.82)
IIIc	4-Morpholinyl	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ NO ₅	75	136-37	62.70 (62.94)	6.05 (6.27)	4.78 (4.59)
IIId	1-Piperidinyl	C ₁₇ H ₂₁ NO ₄	68	157-58	67.12 (67.31)	7.75 (6.98)	4.84 (4.62)
IIIe	1-Pyrrolidinyl	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ NO ₄	72	140-41	66.92 (66.42)	6.45 (6.67)	4.72 (4.84)

TABLE 2—CHARACTERIZATION DATA OF N,N-DISUBSTITUTED MONO AMIDE OF 3(4-METHOXYPHENYL)GLUTACONIC ACID (III)

Compd.	R	Molecular formula	Yield %	m.p. °C	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)		
					C	H	N
III f	H	C ₂₂ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₄	80	168-70	69.82 (69.46)	6.15 (6.36)	7.05 (7.36)
III g	2-CH ₃	C ₂₃ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₄	82	192-98	70.61 (70.08)	6.86 (6.64)	7.70 (7.10)
III h	3-CH ₃	C ₂₃ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₄	75	220-21	70.58 (70.03)	6.15 (6.64)	7.49 (7.10)
III i	4-CH ₃	C ₂₃ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₄	80	180-81	70.64 (70.03)	6.20 (6.64)	7.68 (7.10)
III j	2-Cl	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ ClN ₂ O ₄	90	215-16	63.72 (63.68)	5.72 (5.59)	7.55 (6.76)
III k	3-Cl	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ ClN ₂ O ₄	78	220-21	63.51 (63.68)	5.85 (5.59)	6.25 (6.75)
III l	4-Cl	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ ClN ₂ O ₄	76	199-200	63.95 (63.68)	5.99 (5.59)	6.52 (6.75)

 TABLE 3—CHARACTERIZATION DATA OF N,N-DISUBSTITUTED β -METHYL-*p*-METHOXY CINNAMAMIDES (IV)

Compd.	N $\begin{matrix} \text{R} \\ \diagdown \\ \diagup \\ \text{R} \end{matrix}$	Molecular formula	Yield %	m.p. °C	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)		
					C	H	N
IV a	Dimethylamino	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ NO ₂	79	120-21	71.50 (71.21)	7.90 (7.81)	6.51 (6.38)
IV b	Diethylamino	C ₁₉ H ₂₁ NO ₂	60	119-20	72.44 (72.84)	8.60 (8.56)	5.66 (5.81)
IV c	4-Morpholinyl	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ NO ₂	87	87-88	68.72 (68.94)	7.51 (7.33)	5.48 (5.36)
IV d	1-Piperidinyl	C ₁₈ H ₂₁ NO ₂	80	159-60	74.60 (74.18)	8.31 (8.16)	5.49 (5.40)
IV e	1-Pyrrolidinyl	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ NO ₂	85	95-96	73.58 (73.44)	7.68 (7.81)	5.80 (5.71)

 TABLE 4—CHARACTERIZATION DATA OF N,N-DISUBSTITUTED β -METHYL-*p*-METHOXY CINNAMAMIDE (IV)

Compd.	R	Molecular formula	Yield %	m.p. °C	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)			
					C	H	N	Cl
IV f	H	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₂	98	139-40	74.90 (74.97)	7.10 (7.19)	8.32 (8.38)	—
IV g	2-CH ₃	C ₂₂ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₂	85	189-90	75.58 (75.40)	7.41 (7.48)	7.90 (7.99)	—
IV h	3-CH ₃	C ₂₂ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₂	90	159-60	75.63 (75.40)	7.53 (7.48)	8.10 (7.99)	—
IV i	4-CH ₃	C ₂₂ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₂	87	138-39	75.69 (75.40)	7.58 (7.48)	7.89 (7.99)	—
IV j	2-Cl	C ₂₁ H ₂₂ ClN ₂ O ₂	78	210-11	68.50 (68.00)	6.30 (6.25)	7.05 (7.55)	9.58 (9.56)
IV k	3-Cl	C ₂₁ H ₂₂ ClN ₂ O ₂	82	190-91	68.33 (68.00)	6.20 (6.25)	7.65 (7.55)	9.59 (9.56)
IV l	4-Cl	C ₂₁ H ₂₂ ClN ₂ O ₂	90	187-88	68.41 (68.00)	6.28 (6.25)	7.60 (7.55)	9.51 (9.56)

TABLE 5—CHARACTERIZATION DATA OF N,N-DISUBSTITUTED-3-(4-METHOXYPHENYL)BUTANAMIDE (V)

Compd.	$\begin{matrix} R \\ \diagdown \\ N \\ \diagup \\ R \end{matrix}$	Molecular formula	Yield %	m.p. °C	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)		
					C	H	N
Va	Dimethylamino	C ₁₄ H ₁₈ NO ₂	45	140-41	70.59 (70.55)	8.68 (8.65)	6.36 (6.32)
Vb	Diethylamino	C ₁₆ H ₂₂ NO ₂	50	135-36	72.31 (72.25)	9.32 (9.29)	5.65 (5.61)
Vc	4-Morpholinyl	C ₁₄ H ₂₁ NO ₂	52	79-80	68.50 (68.41)	8.01 (8.03)	5.39 (5.31)
Vd	1-Piperidinyl	C ₁₆ H ₂₃ NO ₂	57	162-63	73.59 (73.52)	8.84 (8.87)	5.31 (5.35)
Ve	1-Pyrrolidinyl	C ₁₄ H ₂₁ NO ₂	61	101-02	72.89 (72.84)	8.54 (8.55)	5.63 (5.66)

TABLE 6—CHARACTERIZATION DATA OF N,N-DISUBSTITUTED-3-(4-METHOXYPHENYL)BUTANAMIDE (V)

Compd.	R	Molecular formula	Yield %	m.p. °C	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)			
					C	H	N	Cl
Vf	H	C ₂₁ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₂	38	100-01	74.61 (74.52)	7.79 (7.74)	8.25 (8.27)	—
Vg	2-CH ₃	C ₂₂ H ₂₈ N ₂ O ₂	40	121-22	74.91 (74.96)	8.05 (8.00)	7.90 (7.94)	—
Vh	3-CH ₃	C ₂₂ H ₂₈ N ₂ O ₂	35	146-47	74.92 (74.96)	8.03 (8.00)	7.91 (7.94)	—
Vi	4-CH ₃	C ₂₂ H ₂₈ N ₂ O ₂	52	160-61	74.94 (74.96)	8.04 (8.00)	7.92 (7.94)	—
Vj	2-Cl	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ N ₂ ClO ₂	37	201-02	67.59 (67.63)	6.71 (6.75)	7.48 (7.51)	9.54 (9.50)
Vk	3-Cl	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ N ₂ ClO ₂	41	196-97	67.58 (67.63)	6.78 (6.75)	7.56 (7.51)	9.52 (9.50)
VI	4-Cl	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ N ₂ ClO ₂	48	188-89	67.69 (67.63)	6.79 (6.75)	7.55 (7.51)	9.51 (9.50)

Study was carried out on groups of 10 mice each. Compounds suspended in Tween-80 (10%) solution were injected intraperitoneally to the mice. The doses selected were 30, 100, 300, 600 and 900 mg/kg body weight. The vehicle was injected to the control group of mice. Animals were observed before and after the administration of various doses more or less continuously for a period of 2 hr. Reduced spontaneous motor activity, ataxia, loss of reflexes, reduced alertness and abnormal gait implied depression of CNS. The approximate LD₅₀ of all the compounds were determined from the deaths records during 24 hr. Among the compounds, IVa, b, f, h and l had shown neither any effect on CNS nor any toxic effect on the test animals upto a dose of 900 mg/kg. Therefore, these compounds were not considered for further screening.

Spontaneous motor activity in mice by actophotometer :

Male mice in groups of six were used in this test. Tween-80 (10%) emulsion in distilled water was injected intraperitoneally to one group of mice and they were placed in the actophotometer and the activity was recorded for 10 min after 0.5 hr (induction period). It was found to be 8765. This group was taken as the control group. For the other group, a drug was injected i.p. in Tween-80 (10%) suspension at a dose 200 mg/kg body weight. Half an hour after the injection of the drug, activity count of each group for 10 min was recorded. The compounds IVc, IVd and IVe showed 21.00, 11.50 and 10.56% decrease in the motor activity. The compounds IVg, IVh, IVj and IVk showed 30.18, 16.08, 34.20 and 18.20% decrease in motor activity, respectively.

Results and Discussion

In the N-aryl piperazine series of the compounds IVg, IVj and Vg, Vj having *ortho* substituted methyl and chloro group respectively on the aryl ring showed good activity. In these two series (IV and V) of the compounds, however, we had not observed any effect of unsaturation on the activity.

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